

Toward Advancing Emotion Recognition in LLMs: A Comparative Study of Prompt Strategies, Few-Shot Learning, and Model Ensembling

Park, J.¹, Mashayekh Esfahan, N.¹, Narayan, A.^{2 3}

¹ Neuromatch Academy, Neuromatch, Inc.

² Oracle Healthcare, Washington, United States

³ Northeastern University, Washington, United States

Keywords: Emotion Recognition, Large Language Models (LLMs), Prompt Engineering, Few-Shot Learning, Model Ensembling

Abstract

Emotion recognition plays a critical role in enhancing human–computer interactions. This study benchmarks the performance of commercial (GPT-4o, Claude–3.5 Sonnet) and open-source (Llama 3.1, Qwen 2.5, Mistral, Gemma 3) large language models (LLMs) on the ISEAR dataset using five prompt strategies: no persona, baseline persona, zero-shot, few-shot, and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG). Structured prompting consistently improved classification accuracy, particularly for smaller open-source models, while commercial models remained robust even under minimal prompt settings. Challenging emotions such as guilt, shame, and disgust exhibited lower classification performance across models. Model ensembling further enhanced results, with the Qwen 2.5 14B ensemble achieving the highest macro-F1 score of 78.4%. These results highlight the effectiveness of structured prompt design and model aggregation in optimizing emotion recognition. Future directions include integrating dimensional emotion frameworks and multimodal signals to build more context-sensitive and resilient systems.

Description

1 Introduction

Emotion recognition is essential for advancing human–computer interactions in fields such as virtual assistants, mental health tracking, and social robotics (Lefter et al., 2024). Earlier approaches used manually engineered features and classical classifiers, which often failed to generalize across diverse texts (Asghar et al., 2017; Berka, 2020; Hung & Alias, 2023). The advent of LLMs, such as GPT (OpenAI et al., 2024) and LLaMa (Touvron et al., 2023), has transformed the field by leveraging comprehensive pretraining on vast text corpora, enabling these models to capture subtle emotional nuances (Annepaka & Pakray, 2025).

A key advancement is the emergence of zero-shot and few-shot emotion classification, where models use textual entailment to map text to established emotion labels without additional task-specific fine-tuning (Yin et al., 2019). While zero-shot classification cuts compute, it hinges on sophisticated prompt engineering to optimize performance across models and datasets (Basile et al., 2021; Plaza-del-Arco et al., 2022).

This study compares two commercial models (GPT-4o and Claude–3.5 Sonnet) with various open-source models (Llama 3.1, Qwen 2.5, Mistral, and Gemma 3) using the ISEAR dataset. We aim to assess each model's ability to classify text into one of seven emotional categories and evaluate the effectiveness of various prompt-based strategies, including not only zero-shot and few-shot classification but also more advanced approaches such as persona-based prompting and retrieval-augmented generation. Additionally, we explore model ensembling techniques to combine the strengths of individual models and further enhance performance.

2 Methods

2.1 Dataset

The ISEAR dataset (Scherer & Wallbott, 1994), derived from psychological research, contains self-reported emotional experiences from diverse cultural backgrounds. Each entry includes a brief narrative paired with one of seven emotion labels: joy, fear, anger, sadness, shame, guilt, and disgust. Its diverse, rich emotional expressions provide a realistic benchmark for evaluating LLMs in emotion classification. After filtering irrelevant and duplicate entries (see Supplementary Section 2), 7,328 ISEAR samples remained.

2.2 Models

- **Open-Source:** Llama 3.1 (8B) (Grattafiori et al., 2024), Qwen 2.5 (Yang et al., 2024), Mistral (7B), Gemma 3
- **Commercial:** GPT-4o, Claude–3.5 Sonnet.

2.3 Parameters

All experiments used a fixed seed (42) and temperature (0.1); full settings in Supplementary Section 3. Experiments were conducted without any additional task-specific fine-tuning.

2.4 Prompt Engineering

All prompt strategies followed a shared structure with an instruction and output formatting, differing mainly in the inclusion of persona settings, emotion definitions, and few-shot examples as additional context. Detailed components and templates are provided in Supplementary Section 5 and 6.

2.5 Experimental Setups

We conducted four experiments to investigate how prompt engineering, model size, emotion specificity, and ensembling affect LLM-based emotion recognition. All prompt strategies shared a core template (Instruction and Output format) and gradually added.

2.5.1 Prompt Strategies

Three open-source LLMs of similar size (Llama 3.1, Qwen 2.5, Mistral; \approx 7B parameters) were each run under five prompting setups (No Persona, Persona Baseline, Zero-Shot, Few-Shot, RAG) on ISEAR dataset, measuring macro precision, recall, and F1- score. This experiment was designed to assess how prompt structure impacts model performance.

2.5.2 Model Size Effects

Prompt strategies were repeated at three different model sizes of Gemma 3 (1B, 4B, 12B) and Qwen 2.5 (1.5B, 7B, 14B) to assess how performance gains vary with model scale, including comparisons against large commercial models such as GPT-4o and Claude-3.5 Sonnet. This provided insights into how model size influences the effectiveness of prompt strategies.

2.5.3 Emotion-Specific Analysis

Class-wise metrics with error bars and confusion matrices were analyzed to identify specific emotion challenges. The unknown ratio (invalid rate) measures instances where the LLM-generated output did not conform to the specified structured format, such as the designated emotion classes.

2.5.4 Ensembling

We employed a prompt-level Mixture of Agents (MoA) technique to combine model outputs.

a) **Proposer Phase:**

Two models (Model A and Model B) independently generated responses to the same input prompt.

b) **Aggregator Phase:**

A third model (Model C) received a combined prompt containing the original user query, the raw outputs from Models A and B, and an additional instruction (e.g., "Synthesize the best elements from both responses").

The final output was generated by Model C through prompt-guided synthesis of the provided responses.

See Supplementary Section 6.6 for details.

2.6 Evaluation Metric

Precision, recall, and F1 score were computed for each emotion class. Final comparisons were based on the macro-averaged F1 score, treating all classes equally.

3 Results

We evaluated the performance of multiple leading large language models—Llama 3.2, GPT-4o, Claude-3.5 Sonnet, Gemma 3, Mistral and Qwen 2.5—using the ISEAR dataset for categorical emotion classification. Additionally, five prompt strategies —**No Persona**, **Persona Baseline**, **Zero-Shot**, **Few-Shot**, and **RAG**—were tested. (Figure 1)

3.1 Prompt Strategy Variation

Across all three 7B open-source LLMs, performance improved steadily as more contextual information was incorporated into the prompts. Removing Persona instructions ("No Persona") resulted in the lowest macro-F1 scores, while RAG retrieval consistently produced the highest gains, surpassing the 60% baseline. This demonstrates the significant impact of contextual information on emotion classification (Figure 1b).

3.2 Model Size Effects

Larger models exhibited smaller returns from advanced prompt strategies. The relative improvements from Few-Shot and RAG decreased with increasing model size—an effect most notable in commercial LLMs—although absolute performance remained high. This suggests that larger models already capture emotional nuances well through extensive pretraining, reducing the need for additional prompt guidance (Figure 1c).

3.3 Specific Emotion Performance

Subtle emotions such as disgust, shame, and guilt showed unique prediction patterns, with the lowest F1 scores and highest invalid prediction rates. For instance, in the Gemma 3 12B model, these three emotions showed notably lower performance scores as represented in the blue bar graph (Figure 1d, center), where scatter dots represent different prompting conditions with error bars denoting standard error (STDE). These emotions were also frequently misclassified, as evident from the confusion matrices and associated red bar graphs representing unknown ratio (Figure 1d, right). The error rates notably exhibited inverse patterns relative to correct predictions, highlighting systematic difficulties in distinguishing these particular emotional states. These emotions often overlap or are confused with one another, and their nuances may be

difficult to capture through text alone. Complete results for all models are available in Supplementary Figures 1a and 1b.

3.4 Ensemble Improvements

To identify the highest-performing models, we conducted a detailed review of results across emotion classes and averaged metrics. Two model-prompt combinations demonstrated superior performance: GPT-4o with RAG (achieving F1 scores of 96.1 for joy, 71.6 for anger, 74.6 for disgust, and 67.5 for shame, with a macro-average F1 of 78.0) and Claude 3.5 Sonnet (achieving F1 scores of 78.2 for sadness and 75.9 for guilt, with a macro-average F1 of 78.2) as shown in Figure 1f and detailed in Supplementary Figure 1c.

We tested whether open-source models benefit from commercial outputs by including top model predictions in their prompts during ensemble experiments.

Combining GPT-4o and Claude-3.5 achieved a >6% absolute gain in macro-F1, with the Qwen 2.5 14B as an aggregator reaching the highest macro-F1 of 78.4%, demonstrating the effectiveness of model ensembling. The ensemble approach was able to leverage the strengths of each model, combining them in complementary ways to enhance overall performance (Figs. 1e–f).

Figure 1. Comparative emotion-classification experiments across prompt strategies, model sizes, and ensemble methods. **(a) Prompt configurations.** Five prompt strategies were mainly experimented. They share a core Instruction + Output template. Added components are Personas, Definitions, few-shot examples, and RAG-retrieved examples. **(b) 7B-model performance.** Macro-averaged precision, recall, and F1 for Llama3.1, Qwen2.5, and Mistral under No-Persona, Baseline, Zero-Shot, Few-Shot, and RAG prompts. Light-blue = No Persona; blue = Baseline/Zero-Shot/Few-Shot; purple = RAG. Red dotted line = 60% baseline. **(c) Model-size effects.** Relative gains from the same five prompts, shown for Gemma3 and Qwen2.5 at 7B, 12B, and larger scales. Larger models show reduced incremental benefit, though RAG still gives the biggest absolute lift. **(d) Class-level analysis (Gemma3 12B).** (Left) Normalized confusion matrix. (Center) Precision, recall, and F1 by emotion (error bars = SE; scatter dots = prompt variants). (Right) Unknown-prediction rate by emotion and prompt. **(e) Ensemble pipeline.** GPT-4o and Claude-3.5 outputs feed into an ensembling prompt (pairwise comparisons + confidence weighting), yielding a JSON response that Gemma3 12B or Qwen2.5 14B converts into the final label. **(f) Detailed F1 results.** Class-wise and macro-F1 for six conditions: GPT-4o (RAG), Claude-3.5 (RAG), Qwen2.5 14B (RAG), Gemma3 12B (RAG), and their respective ensembles. Best scores are green, worst are red.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

This study highlights the effectiveness of structured prompt engineering in enhancing LLM-based emotion recognition. Open-source models steadily improved as components such as Persona instructions, Emotion Definitions, and RAG-retrieved examples were incorporated, whereas commercial models demonstrated robust performance even with simpler prompts, reflecting the advantages of extensive pretraining and fine-tuning.

Guilt, shame, and disgust remain the hardest classes, likely due to their overlap and contextual nuances, further complicating the model's ability to learn consistent patterns.

Although large commercial models consistently outperformed open-source counterparts in absolute terms, the combination of structured prompt design and model ensembling proved highly effective in narrowing the performance gap. Ensemble methods further enhanced classification accuracy, with the Qwen 2.5 14B ensemble achieving the highest macro-F1 score of 78.4%, demonstrating the benefits of combining model strengths.

5 Future Works

Hybrid Strategies: Combine prompt engineering with PEFT (LoRA/Adapters) for targeted adaptation.

Reasoning-Augmented Prompting: Explore reasoning-augmented prompting (CoT, ReACT) for nuanced emotions.

Diverse Dataset Evaluation: Evaluate on diverse, multimodal datasets (e.g., GoEmotions, audio/video).

Dimensional Emotion Modeling: Moving beyond categorical classification toward dimensional emotion modeling—such as the Arousal–Valence frameworks—can offer a richer understanding of emotional expressions, enabling models to capture the continuous nature of human emotions more accurately.

Multimodal Integration: Developing multimodal approaches that combine text, voice, and image data for emotion recognition would enable more comprehensive and accurate emotional analysis.

Acknowledgements

This work was supported by Neuromatch Academy through the Impact Scholars Program. A special thanks to Dr. Arasu Narayan for his essential guidance and assistance during this journey. His mentoring has played a crucial role in shaping our comprehension and progress, and his ongoing support has been a significant source of inspiration. We are genuinely thankful for the chance to gain knowledge from such a motivating mentor.

References

- Annepaka, Y., & Pakray, P. (2025). Large language models: A survey of their development, capabilities, and applications. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 67(3), 2967–3022. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10115-024-02310-4>
- Asghar, M. Z., Khan, A., Bibi, A., Kundi, F. M., & Ahmad, H. (2017). Sentence-Level Emotion Detection Framework Using Rule-Based Classification. *Cognitive Computation*, 9(6), 868–894. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12559-017-9503-3>
- Basile, A., Pérez-Torró, G., & Franco-Salvador, M. (2021). Probabilistic Ensembles of Zero- and Few-Shot Learning Models for Emotion Classification. In R. Mitkov & G. Angelova (Eds.), *Proceedings of the International Conference on Recent Advances in Natural Language Processing (RANLP 2021)* (pp. 128–137). INCOMA Ltd. <https://aclanthology.org/2021.ranlp-1.16/>
- Berka, P. (2020). Sentiment analysis using rule-based and case-based reasoning. *Journal of Intelligent Information Systems*, 55(1), 51–66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10844-019-00591-8>
- Chen, J., Xiao, S., Zhang, P., Luo, K., Lian, D., & Liu, Z. (2024). *BGE M3-Embedding: Multi-Lingual, Multi-Functionality, Multi-Granularity Text Embeddings Through Self-Knowledge Distillation* (No. arXiv:2402.03216). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.03216>
- Esfahani, S. H. N., & Adda, M. (2024). Classical Machine Learning and Large Models for Text-Based Emotion Recognition. *Procedia Computer Science*, 241, 77–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.08.013>
- Grattafiori, A., Dubey, A., Jauhri, A., Pandey, A., Kadian, A., Al-Dahle, A., Letman, A., Mathur, A., Schelten, A., Vaughan, A., Yang, A., Fan, A., Goyal, A., Hartshorn, A., Yang, A.,

- Mitra, A., Sravankumar, A., Korenev, A., Hinsvark, A., ... Ma, Z. (2024). *The Llama 3 Herd of Models* (No. arXiv:2407.21783). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.21783>
- Hung, L. P., & Alias, S. (2023). Beyond Sentiment Analysis: A Review of Recent Trends in Text Based Sentiment Analysis and Emotion Detection. *Journal of Advanced Computational Intelligence and Intelligent Informatics*, 27(1), 84–95.
<https://doi.org/10.20965/jaciii.2023.p0084>
- Lefter, I., Rook, L., & Chaspari, T. (2024). Editorial: Multimodal interaction technologies for mental well-being. *Frontiers in Computer Science*, 6.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fcomp.2024.1412727>
- Lewis, P., Perez, E., Piktus, A., Petroni, F., Karpukhin, V., Goyal, N., Küttler, H., Lewis, M., Yih, W., Rocktäschel, T., Riedel, S., & Kiela, D. (2021). *Retrieval-Augmented Generation for Knowledge-Intensive NLP Tasks* (No. arXiv:2005.11401). arXiv.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2005.11401>
- OpenAI, Achiam, J., Adler, S., Agarwal, S., Ahmad, L., Akkaya, I., Aleman, F. L., Almeida, D., Altschmidt, J., Altman, S., Anadkat, S., Avila, R., Babuschkin, I., Balaji, S., Balcom, V., Baltescu, P., Bao, H., Bavarian, M., Belgum, J., ... Zoph, B. (2024). *GPT-4 Technical Report* (No. arXiv:2303.08774). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2303.08774>
- Plaza-del-Arco, F. M., Martín-Valdivia, M.-T., & Klinger, R. (2022). Natural Language Inference Prompts for Zero-shot Emotion Classification in Text across Corpora. In N. Calzolari, C.-R. Huang, H. Kim, J. Pustejovsky, L. Wanner, K.-S. Choi, P.-M. Ryu, H.-H. Chen, L. Donatelli, H. Ji, S. Kurohashi, P. Paggio, N. Xue, S. Kim, Y. Hahm, Z. He, T. K. Lee, E. Santus, F. Bond, & S.-H. Na (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Computational Linguistics* (pp. 6805–6817). International Committee on Computational Linguistics. <https://aclanthology.org/2022.coling-1.592/>
- Scherer, K. R., & Wallbott, H. G. (1994). Evidence for universality and cultural variation of differential emotion response patterning. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*,

66(2), 310–328. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.66.2.310>

Touvron, H., Lavril, T., Izacard, G., Martinet, X., Lachaux, M.-A., Lacroix, T., Rozière, B., Goyal, N., Hambro, E., Azhar, F., Rodriguez, A., Joulin, A., Grave, E., & Lample, G. (2023).

LLaMA: Open and Efficient Foundation Language Models (No. arXiv:2302.13971). arXiv.

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.13971>

Yang, A., Yang, B., Hui, B., Zheng, B., Yu, B., Zhou, C., Li, C., Li, C., Liu, D., Huang, F., Dong,

G., Wei, H., Lin, H., Tang, J., Wang, J., Yang, J., Tu, J., Zhang, J., Ma, J., ... Fan, Z.

(2024). *Qwen2 Technical Report* (No. arXiv:2407.10671). arXiv.

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2407.10671>

Yin, W., Hay, J., & Roth, D. (2019). *Benchmarking Zero-shot Text Classification: Datasets,*

Evaluation and Entailment Approach (No. arXiv:1909.00161). arXiv.

<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1909.00161>